

Role of AI-Supported Hospitality Services in Enhancing Tourists' Satisfaction: A Systematic Review

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Abstract:

As there is digital transformation rapidly in every field, such a way there are too many changes in hospitality tourism industry also. Due to rapid transformation in modern technology from traditional such as using AI-based services in hospitality and tourism industries there is more opportunities for improving customer experience and efficiency in delivering the services. Across the globe there is drastic change in delivering the services which is done via advanced AI-based technology such as chatbots, smart rooms, robotics, analytics for predicting, etc which are reshaping the way of delivering services of hospitality and great experience in tour. This paper discusses how the contribution of AI-based hospitality services is significant in enhancing the satisfaction of tourists by reviewing the literature which is available related to this topic. In this study, the databases have been used to analysed published peer-reviewed research papers during the period of 2015-2025 related to the topic of AI-supported hospitality services and tourism industry. The research focuses on the AI-supported services, customization, understanding, and engagement of customers which are very important factors in strengthening tourist satisfaction. The finding of this research reveals that there is decreasing in delay for delivery of services, enhancing quality of services, customization of services, engagement of customers which transform into satisfaction of tourists. This research paper also provides the conceptual framework about smart tourism infrastructure and actionable improvements to achieve advantage in competition with the help of innovative technology. The conceptual framework in this research which based on the output of review of literature focuses on the relationship between AI-supported services and tourist satisfaction.

Keywords: *AI-Supported Services, Hospitality, Tourists Satisfaction, Experience of Visitors, Tourism Growth*

Introduction:

The hospitality sector is experiencing an innovative change due to the rapid development in technologies and digital revolution. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the powerful technologies that has been transforming the way of delivering services, efficiency in operations, and customer engagement in tourism industry. Hotels are adopting AI-supported system which improve the quality of services and customer experience such as chatbots, facial recognition

technology, automated room systems, service robots, and predictive analysis. In increasing competition of tourism industry, hospitality sectors are also adopting AI-supported solutions to satisfy the changing needs of tourists and provide them customized, efficient and smooth services. The issue of tourist satisfaction is primary concern for long term sustainability of any hospitality sector. Happy and satisfied tourists always think to revisit the destination and recommend to others also which help to promote

through good word of mouth. Modern digital services help hospitality sector by satisfying tourists with providing them quick responses, personalized experiences, reducing waiting times, and error free service delivery. The services which are AI-supported in hospitality sector have better capabilities to fulfil the expectations of the tourists such as providing data to make proper decisions, changing services in real time, and making conversations more accessible.

On the basis of other research, it has been observed that AI-supported services make the operations of hospitality more efficient with automation of routine activities, reducing human errors, and best allocation of resources. Additionally, these tools help hospitality sector to identify the behaviour pattern and the preferences of tourists so that they can offer them customized recommendations, which can increase emotional involvement and make them feel valuable. Smart virtual assistant and robot services also help to enhance accessibility and convenience of customer which are key factors of service quality of hospitality industry. Hence, the implementation of AI-supported services is becoming essential to link with higher satisfaction of tourists and overall service delivery are becoming better.

Though there are many studies about the AI applications in hospitality industry, the existing studies focusing on particular applications rather than offering integrated perspective. Some have studied focusing only on chatbots or service robots or booking systems, etc. Very few research have studied all services of AI. There is a need of theoretical framework regarding the relationship between AI-supported services and higher tourists' satisfaction.

To fill this gap, the current study uses systematic literature review to determine the role of hospitality services which are AI-supported in increasing the satisfaction of tourists. This study combines the outcomes of existing research

relating to AI-supported services and tourists' satisfaction and suggests theoretical frameworks which explain relationships between these variables. This study adds knowledge in existing research by exploring smart system which has been founded by the smart technology and tourism environment such as destinations, hotels, tour agencies, tourists, etc.

Objectives of Study:

1. To understand various AI-supported services adopted by hospitality sector.
2. To examine the relationship between AI-supported services and satisfaction of tourists.
3. To identify the role of AI-supported services in enhancing tourists' experience.
4. To review existing research findings and formulate a theoretical framework which link tourists' satisfaction with AI-supported services.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

This research is descriptive in nature and completely based on concepts related to service quality of hospitality and its impact on the shaping the experience of tourists. This study applies systematic review of literature methodologies to explore the role of AI-supported hospitality services and their impact on tourists' satisfaction. This research focused on reviewing on peer-reviewed journal articles which were published during the period 2015 to 2025 to show the fast development of Artificial Intelligence in hospitality industry.

Literature Review:

The role of Artificial Intelligence has been becoming considerable academic interest in last ten years. In tourism sector, the use of artificial intelligence has become most significant

digital strategy, it is redefining the operational activities of the hospitality services, way of engaging customers, and system of delivering the services. In this study, there is a discussion on the key factors of AI-supported services of hospitality and satisfaction of tourists such as automation of services, improvement in quality of services, customization, and experience of tourists.

Artificial Intelligence in Hospitality Services:

In hospitality sector, the adoption of Artificial Intelligence mainly helps in automation of day-to-day activities, efficiency in operations and increasing good coordination of hospitality internal stakeholders and tourists. Mostly some of the AI tools have been adopted by the hospitality services which are popular such as chatbots, smart room technologies, system of face recognition, robots, and virtual assistance. The most popular technologies have been used by the hospitality services i.e. AI-supported virtual assistants and chatbots which have been become as common feature of websites of hotels and mobile apps which is accessible for 24/7 for customers, for booking, and they are useful for responding to frequently asked questions which help in planning.

The finding of the research shows that the chatbots help to reduce response time and enhances the accessibility of services. Likewise, in many high-end hotels have started to implement robot services for different kinds of activities such as late night services, food serving, providing information about destinations, check-in, check-outs, and housekeeping which enhances efficiency of hospitality sector and reduce workload of human being.

AI-supported smart room technology like Alexa has been adopted by the hospitality sector for controlling lights, air-conditions, voice-controlled services, and offer tourists personalized entertainment. These types of AI-

supported hospitality services support significantly to the hotels for increasing experience of tourists and maximising their convenience. Many high-end hotels use analytics system for understanding pattern of tourists' behaviours, determining pricing strategies, and deciding marketing strategies. All these tools of artificial intelligence have brought drastic change in tradition hospitality sector. Researcher has observed that these technologies have not been studied in single research but studied separately.

AI and Service Quality Enhancement:

Quality of the hospitality sectors is very significant. Artificial intelligence is becoming more popular as mechanism for improving the quality of services such as accuracy in understanding, surety, efficiency, quickness and reliability.

Due to AI-supported services the human errors are minimizing such as data handling, billing procedure, management of reservation, etc. AI-supported services are helpful in increasing reliability and enhancing the experience of tourists. In addition, due to the real time responses increases convenience for tourists as well as for hotels to determine the strategies which increase customer satisfaction. The research also highlights on how AI-supported services maintain consistency in service delivery. AI-supported services work without getting tired like human being but work not stop and give guarantee of consistency. Due to standardization in hospitality sector, tourists' trust and belief about professionalism have been enhanced.

However, some researchers believe that due to over reliance on automation of services can reduce interactions between humans which can impact on affection and emotions of tourists as well as internal stakeholders of hospitality. Hence, there is a need of balance between human

touch and automation of services for successful implementation of AI-supported services.

Overall, literature support to the idea of using AI-supported services strategically so that it has positive impact on hospitality as well as tourism industry.

AI-Supported Personalization and Customer Experience:

One of the most significant capabilities of AI-supported services is providing personalized experiences. The modern tourists demand customized hospitality services hence it can be said that personalization has become one of the primary determinants for increasing experience of tourists. The most important benefit of data analytics of AI-supported systems is that it finds out the patterns of behaviour of each customer, it also maintains history of bookings, habit of spending and also online interaction of each tourist. Customer engagement has been increasing due to customized setting of room, recommendations for dining, travel planning, and offers for targeted tourists.

The finding regarding personalization, the customer experiences has been increased positively which make tourists to visit the destination again and recommend it to others also.

AI-Supported Services and Satisfaction of Tourists :

The most multidimensional concept in hospitality sector is tourists' satisfaction which is dependent on the quality of services, emotional experience, and convenience for the tourists. The contribution of efficiency, accuracy and customization is most significant part of AI-supported services. Due to AI-supported system, tourists need not to wait more for booking, check-in, check-out, and also it improves speed in delivering services which impact positively leads to satisfaction of tourists.

Research Gap:

There are very few research which focuses on all of the tools of AI for hospitality sector which are used for satisfying tourists. Most of studies have highlighted a particular technology or single perspective for hospitality sector without considering their interrelation. And also, the current literature has focused on the effectiveness of the day-to-day activities but not the complete satisfaction outcomes in smart tourism ecosystem. The integration of findings of all reviewed literature and building a theoretical framework which can connect hospitality services which are AI based, quality services, customization with tourists' satisfaction.

The present study addresses the gap between existing literature and conceptual frameworks by reviewing the literature systematically.

Conceptual Frameworks:

In this present study the conceptual frameworks linking AI-Supported hospitality services with satisfaction of tourists have been developed on the basis of existing research related to this topic. The framework shows that AI-supported hospitality services are main set up for increasing satisfaction of tourists through technologies which modify the services and improves quality of service delivery.

The AI-supported technologies in hospitality sector are chatbots, robots for various services, smart room mechanism, analysis for prediction, and recommendation system. These modern technologies are very helpful in reducing waiting time, increasing operational efficiency, respond fast, reduce errors, and mainly consistency in delivery of services.

The personalized services which are AI-driven support to provide services which are preferred by the customers, and it leads satisfaction of the tourists. AI-supported services

support to formulate the strategies for tourist engagement, individual suggestions, and settings of rooms as per customer which simultaneously improves customer satisfaction and experience of tour.

As per the framework, customers' satisfaction and adoption of artificial intelligence in hospitality sector are strongly affected by the quality of services and customer recommended services. While AI-supported system is considered as useful, easy to use, trustworthy, and practical, their positive impact becomes more powerful. On the other hand, the relationship of hospitality sectors' internal stakeholder and tourists may be damaged because of security reasons, privacy, complexity in technology, and decreasing human interaction.

With the goal of increasing satisfaction of the tourists directly as well as indirectly, the AI-Supported hospitality services are considered as strategic intermediaries for smart hospitality ecosystems.

Conclusion:

The increasing adoption of smart technology which is driven by artificial intelligence in hospitality sector is drastically transforming traditional delivery systems and increasing tourist satisfaction. The significant development in technology making easy and possible to provide services quickly and more accurate services to the tourists which leads to higher satisfaction of tourists. The artificial intelligence driven hospitality services has become significant strategies for increasing quality and maintaining competitiveness in the tourism sector as well as hospitality sector.

Recommendations:

1. To increase responsiveness and efficiency in delivering hospitality services, AI-supported technology should be adopted by

the hospitality industry like chatbots, data analytics, and smart room technology.

2. To maintain emotional aspect while delivering the services, managers should keep balance automation and human interactions.
3. To increase confidence of the tourists in AI-supported technologies, the hospitality organizations should ensure the privacy protection and responsibility while managing data.

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